

FORMS OF ORGANIZING MUSICAL COMMUNICATION IN MUSIC LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

Communication is the exchange of information and communication between people arising from the need for cooperative activity. In the article, the author reveals the forms of organizing musical communication in music lessons.

Keywords: pedagogical technology, explanation, information, content, means, method, activity, teaching, mastering, information, meaning and content, soloist, soloist, soloist, musician, singer, sound, musician, song, performance, group singing, melody, opera, ballet, choir and orchestra, means of expression of music, dynamic signs in music, perception, memory, thinking, imagination, speech activity, communication, nonverbal, pantomime.

INTRODUCTION

Before covering the topic of organizing the communication process, let's consolidate our knowledge a little about "Musical Education" and "Organization of Musical Education".

Musical Education. Currently, aesthetic education of teamwork in all general secondary schools, vocational and technical schools, kindergartens and youth is considered one of the main issues of the educational process.

The dry formalism that has prevailed in schools for centuries is being eliminated. The new school is focused on meeting life's demands and needs. It is characterized by unprecedented initiative and activity in the further improvement of aesthetic education, the creation of its forms and methods that are suitable for children's interests. As a result of the development of education and upbringing of the younger generation in general secondary schools in recent years, the position of literature and art in schools has been strengthened.

The main part.

The discipline of pedagogy has developed and improved programs and textbooks. Methodological guides for teachers are being created and new forms of involving teachers in the world of beauty in life and art are being developed.

The emergence of ideas for developing forms and methods of artistic creative activity of teachers outside the classroom and outside the school, as well as the

emergence and strengthening of ideas for developing schools today, are of particular importance.

This is currently the most effective factor for the development of schools.

The practical experience of schools working on the aesthetic education of students shows that they effectively solve the main task with their creative work, that is, they are comprehensively developed, embodying spiritual wealth, moral purity and physical perfection. Therefore, in every school in our republic, aesthetic education is currently considered the most important element of pedagogy in the formation of a personality.

The content of aesthetic education implies the close connection of various forms of artistic and creative activity of children in the classroom and outside the classroom. In order to organize an intensive and developing complex of aesthetic education for children in each school, it is necessary to eliminate the notion that the goals and objectives of aesthetic education are one-sided.

General forms of organization of musical education. Forms of organization of musical education are external features of the musical educational process, determined by the number of its participants and the type of musical activity.

In musical education, it is customary to distinguish the following forms of its organization:

- mass;
- group (club);
- individual.

Communication – is the interaction of two or more people, consisting of the exchange of affective-evaluative and cognitive information.

Communication is the exchange of information between people arising from the need for cooperative activity. The types and forms of communication are diverse.

For example: this is a practical dialogue in the process of professional activity, carried out directly "face to face" and indirectly through technical means, i.e. telegram, telephone, gesture, WhatsApp, message, etc., a conversation between 2 people, a monologue for 1 person, a polylogue for a large number of people.

The functions of communication are:

- To ensure that people understand each other;
- To establish a basis for social experience;
- To prepare for a particular activity, that is, to inspire

The concept of communication. Communication is an important condition of human life and activity. It is through communication that people have the opportunity to master their nature and work together to satisfy their individual needs. In the process of communication, certain images and models of human behavior are formed, which are subsequently embedded in a person. A person's thinking, ability to analyze and evaluate the world and his own image are formed in the process of communication. The Polish psychologist E. Melibruda, who gave a comprehensive assessment of this problem, emphasizes the following: "Communication is as important to us as air in interpersonal relationships."

Since communication is an extremely complex process, it is very difficult to give it a single correct definition. Therefore, usually the content of the concept of communication is described by emphasizing its individual aspects.

A) communication - the process of establishing and developing contact, determined by the need for joint activity.

B) communication - the interaction of subjects through a system of signs.

A.V. The textbook "General Psychology" edited by Petrovsky defines "Communication as a process of information exchange, interaction and mutual understanding between two or more people."

The textbook "General Psychology" edited by M.G. Davletshin states: "Communication is an interaction between two or more people, consisting of an affective-evaluative and cognitive exchange of information."

The brief explanatory dictionary "Psychology" edited by M.G. Davletshin defines communication as follows: "Communication is the interaction of two or more people with each other."

In accordance with the above definitions, communication can be generally defined as follows: communication is a process of interaction between at least two people, during which information is exchanged, relationships are established, and developed.

The concept of communication should be distinguished from the concept of communication. Communication means the exchange of information between living and non-living systems. The exchange of signals between animals, human communication with technical means, all of these are examples of communication. Communication can only be carried out between people. The importance of communication in human life is immeasurable. It is in the process of communicating and interacting with others that a human child becomes a person. Through communication, a person acquires social experience and culture. If a newborn person is deprived of the opportunity to communicate with others, he will never be able to become a person, that is, he will lag behind in his psychic development. After all, the psychic development of a person begins with communication.

There can be no human society without communication. It is communication that forms a team of individuals working together. In order to draw up a plan of joint activity and implement it, communication between individuals is necessary. Joint activity is organized and carried out through communication. At the same time, new relationships and connections are formed between people during the activity. Therefore, communication and activity are closely interconnected.

We can clearly see how important communication is in human life in the following examples:

Example 1. In 1938, Richard Bard voluntarily spent 6 months in the Antarctic ice. On the one hand, he was interested in the results of the experiment, on the other hand, he wanted to take a break from the hustle and bustle of everyday life. Later, he recalled this period with the following words: "Throughout my life here, every movement, every action, seemed to be more and more meaningless, illogical, and purposeless. Although I am not afraid of danger, for some reason I began to fear that the roof would collapse here. My eating habits became irregular, I stopped washing."

Example 2. In history, the Japanese had a system of self-improvement called "Moritao". However, a person is not subject to any physical suffering. He simply goes into a cave for a week and remains there alone. Here he could not even talk to himself. Those

who passed the test later happily meet any meeting and conversation. Interestingly, they have not a greater need to talk, but a greater need to listen.

Example 3. At one time, the automation of all restaurants in America was rampant. But soon their owners began to go bankrupt. As it turned out, people came here not only to have a snack, but also to find a conversational partner.

From this it can be seen that people always feel the need for communication and try to satisfy it.

Communication functions also play an important role in the communication process. Communication functions are understood as the functions that communication performs in human life. Communication functions are diverse, and according to the most common classification, namely, proposed by Boris Fyodorovich Lomov, it consists of the following.

- Information-communicative function - the task of ensuring the exchange of information. Information exchange is carried out through various sign systems. Usually, verbal and nonverbal communication are distinguished.

- Regulatory-communicative function - the function of ensuring the regulation of the behavior of interlocutors. Individuals can influence each other's motives, goals, and decision-making in the process of communication verbally, encourage and control their actions, and influence each other's behavior in a stimulating and corrective manner.

- Affective-communicative function - the function of ensuring the regulation of the emotional sphere of a person. Communication is the most important determinant of a person's emotional states. Because various emotional states arise and change in the process of communication.

According to the classification proposed by L.A. Karpenko, the following tasks of communication are distinguished.

- The task of establishing contact - preparing the interlocutor for communication;

- The information task - exchanging certain information, thoughts and plans with the interlocutor;

- Motivation to activity - stimulating the interlocutor to perform an action;

- Coordination task - organizing joint activities with the interlocutor and coordinating actions in its implementation;

- The task of ensuring understanding - understanding the thoughts and feelings of the interlocutor;

- Amotive task - arousing certain emotions in the interlocutor and changing them;

- Establishing a relationship - determining his personal place, position in the system of relationships;

- Influence - changing the behavior, personal characteristics, goals and attitudes of the interlocutor.

The communicative side of communication. During joint activities, people share various thoughts, ideas, and feelings. In this case, thoughts and feelings can be interpreted as information, and communication as the exchange of information. However, it should be noted that interpersonal communication does not consist simply

of the exchange of information. Because in the process of communication, information is not only transmitted, but also formed, clarified, and developed. Therefore, a person cannot consider communication as a process consisting solely of the exchange of information. After all, firstly, in the process of communication, information does not simply move from one side to the other, but is actively exchanged (when participants in the communicative process send information to each other, they analyze each other's motives, goals, attitudes, etc.); secondly, during the process of communication, people can influence each other through signs (in the process of interpersonal information exchange, of course, a certain influence is exerted on the behavior of the interlocutor); thirdly, in the communication process, the communicator (the person sending the information) and the recipient (the person receiving the information) must have the same coding system; fourthly, in the communication process, obstacles that are unique to interpersonal communication may arise.

There are several systems of signs used in the communicative process. They are verbal communication (through speech) and nonverbal (through signs that are not related to speech) communication.

Verbal communication. Human speech is used as a system of signs. Speech consists of sound signals or written signs used by a person, through which information received from communication is processed, stored and transmitted. This process is carried out through language. Language is a system of verbal signs, which is formed as a product of mental activity in the process of communication.

Language is a means of communication. Language provides communication between those entering into communication, because it is understood by both the sender and the receiver. The person who gives information to another person (communicator) and the receiver (recipient) must use the same language in the process of communication, otherwise they cannot understand each other correctly. The exchange of information must have a sign and content that is understandable to the participants in the communication. Language consists of a set of verbal signs. The meaning of a word is its substantive aspect. In each communication, the actions and activities of a person and the actions and activities of another person are determined by 3 important factors.

□ First, it determines the socio-historical experience of all mankind or a somewhat narrow group of people. A small child does not independently learn the world. He asks his parents questions, and they answer him, from these answers the child receives only a small part of the general knowledge that he will later use in his activities. This small part of general knowledge the child can form in the form of language, in the system of word signs with the help of language. The same thing happens at school, the student acquires all knowledge about the world from the teacher's explanation or from the textbook, that is, with the help of language. Here language appears as a means of fulfilling one of its important functions, namely as a means of living, a means of transmitting and mastering socio-historical experience.

□ Secondly, the actions and activities of each individual person often determine the direct experiences of other people, who do not have social value. For example, I am heading towards the kitchen. On the way, my friend meets me and says: "The kitchen is closed." At this moment, this message somehow directs my activity: I turn around and

go to another kitchen. Here language appears with its other important function, namely as a means or method of communication or a means of controlling the behavior of the world. As a result, any communication, any relationship consists in influencing the interlocutor.

□ Thirdly, the actions and activities of each individual person are determined by the personal experience of each individual person. A person's "personal" own individual experience consists of a unique mixture of the experiences of other people and social experience. Unlike animals, a person can plan his actions. The main tool for such planning and solving general intellectual problems is language. Here we have come across the third function of language as a tool for mental activity (perception, memory, thinking, imagination). Language, as a system of word signs, is used in speech activity.

Speech activity. Speech activity is the process of using language by a person to master and pass on socio-historical experience to generations or to establish communication, to plan his actions. Language is a means of communication or a weapon, and speech activity or speech is the communication process itself. In this process, active and passive types of speech activity are distinguished. The speaker's speech is considered active speech, the listener's speech is considered passive speech. Speech is divided into internal and external speech. External speech is divided into written and oral speech, and oral speech is divided into monologue and dialogical speech. Monologue is a speech of one person addressed to himself or others. This is a teacher's statement, a student's full answer, a lecture, etc. Monological speech has certain difficulties.

Speech is the use of language in the processes of expressing and exchanging ideas, a specific form of language as a separate type of social activity. Speech is understood as the processes of its oral (sound) and written manifestation, that is, the process of speaking and its result (speech thoughts, works stored in memory or recorded in writing).

Visual communication. The "eye contact" sign system is also used in visual communication. This system is of great importance in the work of teachers and leaders.

The interactive aspect of communication. The interactive aspect of communication refers to the interaction of participants in communication in the organization and implementation of joint activities. Through communication, people organize joint activities. Participating in common activities, people influence each other.

Empathy is a person's desire to understand the experiences and feelings of another person by putting himself in the place of his imaginary interlocutor. This means approaching the emotional problems of a person. This is the ability to sympathize with the feelings and experiences of another person.

Communication in pedagogical activity. The concept of communication. The interaction of a person with the world around him is manifested in a system of objective relationships, objective relationships and connections necessarily arise in any real groups. These objective relationships of group members are reflected in subjective interpersonal relationships. Any production requires the unity of people. No human society can organize full-fledged, joint activities if it does not establish relationships with people, they cannot properly understand each other. For example, a teacher must enter into relationships with students in order to teach them something.

Communication in pedagogical activity.

- a means of fulfilling educational tasks;
- a socio-psychological system for ensuring the educational process;
- a method of organizing the interaction between teachers and students, ensuring the success of the educational process;
- manifests itself as a process of educating the individual characteristics of the student.

Pedagogical communication is the emotional background of educational processes, the means and content of communication.

For communication to be successful, it must have feedback, that is, the subject must receive information about the results of the interaction. The communicator learns how the recipient perceives the information he transmits and how he reacts based on the feedback information. Perception of the interlocutor or listener in communication is the main condition for understanding each other. If the teacher cannot understand how his students perceive and understand him, the pedagogical relationship will not be good. This is especially important when giving a lecture. The teacher forms the emotional background and instrumental content of the educational process of this communication. Communication is an interaction between two or more people, manifested in the exchange of information in the form of knowledge or evaluation.

CONCLUSION

We have also given examples of the types and functions of communication in the topic. In cooperative activities, due to necessity, a person must unite with other people, enter into relationships with them, establish contact, achieve mutual understanding, receive the necessary information, and give an appropriate response. In this case, communication is manifested as one side of activity, its information aspect - communication. However, along with creating an object, a person "translates" himself into the object he created, that is, continues himself in others. The created object (a building seen, lines written, a tree drawn) is, on the one hand, the subject of activity, and on the other hand, a means by which a person shows himself. Because it is created for other people. Thus, activity is a part of communication, its side; communication is a part and side of activity. But communication and activity in all cases form a single (indestructible) unity.

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